

Some Substituted Thioureas and Their Reactions with the Platinum Metal Ions

S. C. SHOME, M. MAZUMDER, P. K. HALDAR and D. K DAS*

Chemical Laboratory, Presidency College, Calcutta

Manuscript received 5 January 1976, revised 30 March 1977, accepted 22 April 1977.

Some substituted thioureas have been prepared and their reactions with the platinum metal ions have been studied. The results indicate that the thiourea derivatives, *N*-phenyl-*N'*-acetyl thiourea, *N*- α -pyridyl-*N'*-benzoyl thiourea and *N*- α -(5-bromopyridyl)-*N'*-benzoyl thiourea are potential analytical reagents for the determination of those metals.

A survey of literature reveals that amongst the different classes of sulphur containing ligands, thiourea¹ and substituted thioureas² play an important role in the determination of platinum metals. Attempts³ were made to improve upon the selectivity and sensitivity of the colour reactions of thiourea with the platinum metal ions substituting the hydrogen atoms of the reagent by various groups. Although thiourea and alkyl, aryl or -NHR substituted thioureas offer sensitive colour reactions with the platinum metals, they, however, suffer from lack of selectivity and their metal complexes are also unsuitable for gravimetry by direct weighing.

It is considered that the introduction of an acyl group on one of the nitrogen atoms of the thiourea molecule may yield a better reagent for analytical purposes. The availability of an extra oxygen atom as donor in addition to nitrogen and sulphur in the thiourea molecule may increase the potentiality of the ligand towards complexation. Further the substitution of a hydrogen atom of the second nitrogen atom of the thiourea molecule with a pyridyl group, instead of an alkyl or aryl group, may enhance the basic character of the ligand resulting in an increased solubility of the ligand in polar solvents.

In view of the above considerations, the following reagents have been prepared in the present research and their analytical properties have been studied thoroughly.

- I. *N*-phenyl-*N'*-benzoyl thiourea.
- II. *N*-phenyl-*N'*-acetyl thiourea.
- III. *N*-(2-nitrophenyl)-*N'*-benzoyl thiourea.
- IV. *N*-(2-nitrophenyl)-*N'*-acetyl thiourea.
- V. *N*-(4-nitrophenyl)-*N'*-benzoyl thiourea.
- VI. *N*-(4-nitrophenyl)-*N'*-acetyl thiourea.
- VII. *N*- α -pyridyl-*N'*-benzoyl thiourea.

- VIII. *N*- α -pyridyl-*N'*-acetyl thiourea.
- IX. *N*- α -(5-bromopyridyl)-*N'*-benzoyl thiourea.
- X. *N*- α -(5-bromopyridyl)-*N'*-acetyl thiourea.
- XI. *N*- α -pyridyl-*N'*-(3-nitrobenzoyl) thiourea.
- XII. *N*- α -pyridyl-*N'*-(4-nitrobenzoyl) thiourea.

Experimental

Preparation and Analysis of Thiourea Derivatives:
General method of preparation: All the acyl substituted thioureas of the type R-NH-C-NH-C-R'

[R=Phenyl, nitrophenyl, pyridyl, bromopyridyl; R'=Benzoyl, acetyl, nitrobenzoyl] were prepared by the following general procedure. Ammonium thiocyanate (0.1 mole) was dissolved in acetone and 0.1 mole of the respective acylating agent (R'.CO. Cl) was added slowly with constant shaking. The mixture was refluxed for 15 minutes on a hot water bath, cooled to room temperature and filtered. A solution of 0.1 mole of the corresponding amine (R.NH₂) in acetone was slowly added to the filtrate and mixed well with shaking. The mixture was refluxed for 10 minutes on a hot water bath and most of the acetone was removed by distillation. The residue was added slowly in crushed ice taken in a beaker with constant stirring until the reagent solidified. The crude reagent was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

The results of analysis of the thiourea derivatives are given in Table-1. The nitrogen content was determined by Kjeldahl's method (Reagent Nos. 1 to 6) and by Dumas method (reagent Nos. 7 to 12). Sulphur and bromine were estimated gravimetrically as barium sulphate and silver bromide respectively after decomposition of the compounds with sodium peroxide.

*Present Address: Central Ground Water Board, E. R.,
24, Park Street, Cal-16.

TABLE 1

Ligand	Molecular formula	M.P.	% Nitrogen		% Sulphur		% Bromine	
			Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found
1.	$C_{14}H_{12}N_2OS$	150°	10.93	10.89	12.5	12.46	—	—
2.	$C_9H_{10}N_2OS$	174°	14.43	14.42	16.49	16.50	—	—
3.	$C_{14}H_{11}N_2O_3S$	131°	13.95	13.90	10.63	10.61	—	—
4.	$C_9H_9N_2O_3S$	163°	17.57	17.50	13.38	13.37	—	—
5.	$C_{14}H_{11}N_2O_3S$	152°	13.95	13.92	10.63	10.65	—	—
6.	$C_9H_9N_2O_3S$	177°	17.57	17.46	13.38	13.39	—	—
7.	$C_{13}H_{11}N_2OS$	144°	16.34	16.35	12.45	12.42	—	—
8.	$C_8H_9N_2OS$	158°	21.53	21.51	16.41	16.40	—	—
9.	$C_{13}H_{10}N_2OSBr$	160°	12.50	12.52	9.52	9.50	23.80	23.81
10.	$C_8H_8N_2OSBr$	182°	15.32	15.30	11.67	11.65	29.19	29.18
11.	$C_{13}H_{10}N_4O_3S$	120°	18.54	18.52	10.59	10.60	—	—
12.	$C_{13}H_{10}N_4O_3S$	180°	18.54	18.55	10.59	10.57	—	—

Results and Discussion*Metal Chelates and their Properties*

(a) *Metal chelates of N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea (VII)*: The ligand possesses excellent chelating ability with all the platinum metals and the properties of the chelates are summarized in the Table-2. The empirical formulae of the complexes were assigned by the mole-ratio method as described by Meyer and Ayres⁴.

(iii) The chelates are of definite composition and thermally stable.

(iv) The complexes are of different colour and easily extractable in organic solvents.

(v) The deep coloured extracts of the complexes in ethanol-chloroform mixture are stable for more than 24 hours.

(b) *Metal chelates of N- α -(5-bromopyridyl)-N'-benzoyl thiourea (IX)*: The conditions for the reac-

TABLE-2 CHELATES FORMED BY N- α -PYRIDYL-N'-BENZOYL THIOUREA WITH PLATINUM METALS

Metal ion	Condition of complex formation	Colour of complex	Extractable in	Ligand to metal ratio in the complex	M.P. of chelate
Ru(III)	Hot acetate buffer medium, pH 3.7-5.2	Deep brown	Ethanol chloroform mixture	2 : 1	170°
Rh(III)	Hot acetate buffer medium, pH 3.5-5.5	Brown	-do-	3 : 1	162°
Pd(II)	Dil. hydrochloric acid, 1.6(N)-0.08(N)	-do-	-do-	1 : 1	158°
Ir(III)	Hot acetate buffer medium, pH 4.2-5.86	Orange yellow	-do-	3 : 1	172°
Os(VI)	Hot acetate buffer medium, pH 3.1- 6.2	Dark green	-do-	2 : 1	260°
Pt(IV)	Hot acetate buffer medium, pH 4.06-6.2	Yellow	-do-	2 : 1	160°
Pt(II)	Hot and dilute hydrochloric acid, 0.5(N) to 2.01(N)	Brown	-do-	1 : 1	195°

TABLE-3 CHELATE FORMED BY N- α -(5-BROMOPYRIDYL)-N'-BENZOYL THIOUREA WITH THE PLATINUM METAL IONS.

Metal ions	Condition for complex formation	Colour of complex	Extractable in	Ligand to metal ratio in complex
Ru(III)	Hot acetate buffer medium, pH 4.7-6.4	Deep brown	Ethanol-chloroform mixture	2 : 1
Rh(III)	Hot acetate buffer medium, pH 6.2-7.1	Deep yellow	-do-	3 : 1
Pd(II)	Cold acetate buffer medium, pH 3.8-6.1	Deep brown	-do-	1 : 1
Os(VI)	Hot acetate buffer medium, pH 2.24-3.2	Dark green	-do-	2 : 1
Ir(III)	Hot acetate buffer medium, pH 4.9-6.2	Orange yellow	-do-	3 : 1
Pt(IV)	Hot acetate buffer medium, pH 2.02-2.6	Deep yellow	-do-	2 : 1

N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea is likely to serve as an ideal analytical reagent for both the gravimetric and spectrophotometric purposes due to the following reasons :

- (i) The reagent is appreciably soluble in hot water whereas the chelates are insoluble and they can be easily freed from excess reagent.
- (ii) The complex formation reactions could be made selective in most of the cases by proper control of pH, temperature etc.

ions of the ligand with the platinum metals and the properties of the chelates formed are given in the Table-3.

The reagent cannot be recommended for the gravimetric purpose due to its insolubility in water. However, it could be employed for the spectrophotometric determination of the platinum metals due to following reasons :

- (i) The complexes are formed under different conditions of the reaction media.

- (ii) The complexes are highly coloured and easily extractable in organic solvents.
- (iii) The colour of the ethanol-chloroform extracts of the complexes are stable for more than 24 hours.
- (iv) The chelation takes place under the same condition of acidity.
- (v) Most of the complexes cannot be extracted completely with the common organic solvents.

(c) *Metal chelates of N-phenyl-N'-acetyl thiourea (II)*: The preliminary investigation of the reactions between the platinum metal ions and the reagent indicate that the chelates are partly soluble in water. Palladium (II), rhodium (III) and platinum (IV) produce similar colour reactions with the ligand under similar conditions of acidity. On the other hand the colour reactions with ruthenium (III) and osmium (VI) in 50% ethanol seem to be selective.

The remaining ligands (I, III, IV, V, VI, VIII, X, XI and XII) can not be employed for the determination of the platinum metals due to the following disadvantages:

- (i) Most of them are insoluble in water.
- (ii) Poorly soluble in ethanol.
- (iii) The chelates formed are of hydrated in nature and partly soluble in water.

The preliminary studies of the reactions between the twelve substituted thioureas and the platinum group of metals were undertaken with a view to examine the possibility of application of those reagents in preference to thiourea itself. Among those, N-phenyl-N'-acetyl thiourea produces fairly sensitive and selective colour reactions with osmium (VI) and ruthenium (III) but it is unsuitable for the gravimetry of these platinum metals. The reagent N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea seems to possess potentiality as an ideal analytical reagent for the gravimetric and spectrophotometric determination of the noble metals. N- α -(5-bromopyridyl)-N'-benzoyl thiourea is a more sensitive reagent for the colorimetry of the platinum metals, especially of osmium (VI). The compound is, however, not suitable for the gravimetric determination of these metals. These three thiourea derivatives are found to be quite sensitive and more selective than thiourea in the analysis of platinum metals as can be seen from Table 4.

TABLE-4 COMPARISON OF ANALYTICAL PROPERTIES OF THIOUREA AND SOME SUBSTITUTED THIOUREAS.

Reagents	Determination of Ruthenium		Determination of Osmium		Determination of Palladium	
	Range (ppm)	Interferences	Range (ppm)	Interferences	Range (ppm)	Interferences
1. Thiourea	2-15	Rh, Ir, Pt & Os	5-50	Pd, Ru	0.8-24	
2. N-phenyl-N'-acetyl thiourea	1-20	None	2-25	Rh		
3. N- α -pyridyl-N'-benzoyl thiourea	1-8	None	0.5-25	None	0.5-12	None
4. N- α -(5-bromo-pyridyl)-N'-benzoyl thiourea	0.5-5	None	6.0-30	None	0.3-5	None

* No quantitative data available.

References

- L. TSCHUGAEFF, *Compt. Rend.*, 1918, 167, 253.
- I. HOFFMAN, J. E. SCHWEITZER, D. E. RYAN, F. E. BEAMISH, *Analyt. Chem.*, 1953, 25, 1091.
- B. STEIGER, *Mikrochemie*, 1934, 16, 193.
- A. S. MEYER and G. H. AYRES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 49.
- F. E. BEAMISH, "The analytical chemistry of Noble Metals", Pergamon Press, Student Edition, 1966, p. 369, 395 and 429.

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for the grant of fellowships to P.K.H. and D.K.D.